

PHYSIOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF MAHUA (*Madhuca longifolia*) SEED AND OIL

Maneesh Sonkar, Pisalkar, P. S., Mishra, N. K. and Khokhar, D.

Department of Agricultural Processing and Food Engineering,
Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Raipur (Chhattisgarh), India.

(MS Received: 26.01.2024; MS Revised:28.02.2024; MS Accepted:01.03.2024)

MS 3168

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL PROCESSING AND FOOD ENGINEERING)

Abstract:

The study was conducted to investigate some physico-chemical properties of mahua seed and its oil. The physical properties i.e. seed dimensions, bulk density, true density, porosity, angle of repose and static coefficient of friction against different materials surfaces and the proximate composition of whole seed were determined. In case of seed oil the chemical properties like specific gravity (SG), refractive index (RI), acid value (AV), free fatty acid (FFA), saponification value (SV), peroxide value (PV) and antioxidant property were determined. The average length, width, thickness of mahua seed was 22.76 mm, 11.42 mm and 6.38 mm respectively. The value of bulk density, true density, porosity and angle of repose of mahua seed was found to be 498.36 kg/m³, 1009 kg/m³, 50.2% and 37.19° respectively. In moisture content, oil, protein, fibre, ash and carbohydrates present in dried mahua seed was 4.80% (wb), 41%, 15.34%, 3.57%, 3.19%, and 24% respectively. The acid value of mahua oil was 10.4 ± 1.08 mgKOH/g of with 5.20 ± 0.56% free fatty acid having specific gravity and refractive index of 0.908 ± 0.003 and 1.4638 ± 0.0003 respectively. The peroxide value of oil was 9.8 ± 0.77 meq/kg oil with saponification value of 185.39 ± 6.27 mg KOH/g oil.

Key words - physico-chemical, mahua seed, chemical properties, acid value.

Introduction:

The mahua (*Madhuca longifolia*) is a massive tree with a height of up to 20 meters. It belongs to the family *Sapotaceae* and originated in Southeast Asia. It is a deciduous tree with spreading branches and a large rounded crown of medium to large size. Under dry tropical and subtropical conditions, the seeds grow widely and are either double convex or flattened on one or both sides. Mahua is well-known in tribal areas for its medicinal value and second for its liquor which is made from Mahua flowers. This liquor is also used to make vinegar. The several parts of the mahua tree, like the flowers, seeds, and bark, are very useful. This tree is respected by tribals in Central India for its significance to their rituals and healing properties. In local language Mahua's flowers and seeds are referred to as *Tora* (Ekka and Ekka., 2014). In the tribal culture, the tree has religious and aesthetic significance.

Mahua (*Madhuca longifolia*) blossoms seasonally and produces green pulpy natural fruit containing three to four ellipsoidal seeds. The Mahua tree can produce 18 to 42 kg of seeds annually (Mishra and Pradhan., 2013). Mahua plants have the potential to produce approximately 60 MT of seeds per year in India (Atabani *et al.*, 2013). In Chhattisgarh, the annual marketing potential of Mahua seeds is approximately worth 80 crores. (CGMNFP). Mahua trees are also found abundant in West Bengal, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Orissa, Uttar Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, and Karnataka. The Mahua fruit seeds contain 48 to 50% oil (w/w) and are eaten in raw or in cooked form by tribal (Marikkar *et al.*, 2010). After oil extraction the leftovers cake is used as biomass fuel. The Mahua oil remains in liquid or semi-solid form at ambient condition under tropical temperatures and the colour of the oil is pale yellow.

In case of mahua seed and its oil a very less information is available on physical and chemical properties. Thus, the study was aim to determined the basic physical properties and some chemical properties of oil which will be useful as base line for further research on value addition of mahua seed and its oil.

Materials and method:

Procurement of material: The fresh, mature, and healthy seeds of mahua were procured from local market of Raipur (Chhattisgarh). The mature dehulled seeds (splits) were used for given study. The oil from mahua seeds was extracted by using mini oil mill at temperature of 80°C with screw speed of 72 rpm. The extracted oil was centrifuge (6000 rpm), filtered and stored in dark colored bottle at room temperature for further study.

Physical properties:

Dimensions: Dimensions of mahua seeds were determined using a manual vernier calipers having least count of 0.02 mm, all the three axial dimensions length (L), width (b) and thickness (t) of seeds were measured perpendicular to each. The healthy, cleaned and fresh mahua seeds were chosen for dimension measurement.

Bulk Density (ρ_b): The standard weight test procedure was used to determine the average bulk density (ρ_b) of the seed. The sample was

filled into a measuring cylinder of 500 mL from a certain height. Then the quantity is weighed in a weighing balance (Aczel, CTG 3). The formula for bulk density is:

$$\text{Bulk Density (kg/m}^3\text{)} = \frac{\text{Weight of the seeds (kg)}}{\text{Volume of seeds (m}^3\text{)}}$$

True Density (ρ_t): The true density (ρ_t) of mahua seed was determined by using the toluene displacement method. A sample of (100 g) was immersed in a 500 mL graduated measuring cylinder in which toluene (300 mL) was filled and the top was levelled off. The amount of displaced toluene was noted. The average true density was calculated as it is the ratio of the weight of the seed sample to the volume of toluene displaced. The formula for true density is:

$$\text{True density (kg/m}^3\text{)} = \frac{\text{Weight of the seeds (gm)}}{\text{volume of the toluene displaced (ml)} \times 1000}$$

2.2.4 Porosity: From bulk density (ρ_b) and true density (ρ_t) the porosity was calculated by using the following equation. The porosity (ϵ) was calculated using equation:

$$\text{Porosity} = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_b}{\rho_t}\right) \times 100$$

2.2.5 Angle of repose: The angle of repose determines the maximum angle of the pile of seeds in the horizontal plane. The size, shape, orientation, and moisture content of mahua seeds impacted the angle of repose. To determine the angle of repose, a box structure was used that had a cylindrical cone, with a wooden panel placed in the medial of the cone which had a known diameter. To find the angle of repose, first cover the end of the cone with mahua seeds. Then, after filling, the cover is removed. Also, the front glass panel was removed to allow the bran to flow to its natural slope. The height of the heap is noted. The angle of repose was calculated using the following formula:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{2(H_2 - H_1)}{D} \right]$$

Where,

θ = angle of repose

H_2 = Height of heap

H_1 = Height of table, (cm)

D = Diameter of table, (cm)

2.2.6 Coefficient of static friction: The coefficient of friction was computed by using various surfaces (SS, G.I. and MS plate) that were placed one by one on a moveable plane. Mahua seed was placed over the surface. The movable plane was slowly lifted to a position whereby the mahua seed had just begun to slide down to the plane. The plane existed at this position and the angle of friction was noted. The coefficient of friction was calculated by the following formula: The coefficient of friction

$$\mu = \tan \theta$$

Where,

μ = Coefficient of static friction

θ = Angle of static friction

2.2.7 Specific Gravity of oil: Standardization of pycnometer bottle was done before using it. Melt oil sample to remove the air bubbles and moisture present in oil. After filtering the oil making sure that sample was free of impurities and moisture. Then Fill the dry pycnometer bottle with the prepared sample with ensuring that the no air bubbles trapped in pycnometer. After filling oil sample, stopper was inserted, then immersed in water bath (Bio Technics, India) at 30 ± 2.0 °C and hold for 30 min. to maintain the temperature. Remove the bottle from the bath, clean and dry it thoroughly. Then weight was taken using scientific weighing balance (Shimadzu, ATX224) quickly to ensure that the temperature does not fall below 30°C. specific gravity was calculated by using equation, below.

$$\text{Specific Gravity at } 30^\circ \text{C} \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{ml}} \right) = \frac{A - B}{C - B}$$

Where,

A = weight in g of specific gravity bottle with oil at 30 °C

B = weight in g of specific gravity bottle at 30 °C

C = weight in g of specific gravity bottle with water at 30 °C

2.2.8 Refractive index of oil: The digital refractometer (DG-NXT) was calibrated by using distilled water. The oil sample was Melted using hot air oven (MAC, OUD-224) liquify and filtered through a filter paper to remove impurities and traces of moisture. The temperature of oil was adjusted at 25°C using water bath (Bio Technics, India). Then few drops of the oil sample on the refractometer. The digital instrument shows reading after few seconds.

2.3 Proximate Composition of Mahua Seeds:

2.3.1 Moisture content: The Moisture content of mahua seed was determined by using standard hot air oven method (AOAC, 2000). To determine the moisture content of mahua seeds, 5-gram sample of mahua seeds were kept it in hot air oven (MAC, OUD-224) and left it for 24 hours at $105 \pm 2^\circ \text{C}$ oven temperature.

$$\text{Moisture content } (W_b) = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W}$$

$$\text{Moisture content } (D_b) = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_d}$$

Where,

W_1 = Initial weight of the sample,

W_2 = Final weight of the sample, (g)

W_w = Weight of water, (g)

$W = W_w + W_d$

W_d = Weight of dry matter, (g)

2.3.2 Oil content: The fat content of mahua seeds was determined by using Soxhlet Plus solvent extraction unit (SOCSPPLUS SCS-03E) method described in AOAC,2000. n-Hexane used as solvent to extract oil from seeds.

$$\text{Oil content} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W}$$

Where,

W_1 = Weight of beaker containing fat, (g)

W_2 = Weight of empty beaker, (g)

W = Weight of sample taken, (g)

2.3.4 Protein content: Protein was determined followed by Micro-Kjeldahl (KjelTron, KDIGB20M) method described in AOAC, 2000. Using the conversion factor 6.25.

Nitrogen(%)

$$= \frac{14.01 \times \text{Titred} - \text{Blank} \times \text{Normality of Solution} \times 100}{\text{Weight Of Sample} \times 1000}$$

$$\text{Amount of protein \%} = \text{Nitrogen (\%)} \times 6.25$$

2.3.5 Ash content: Ash content of mahua seeds was determined by using muffle furnace (Exacta Furnace).5 g fresh grinded mahua seed's powder were weighed and transferred in crucible. crucibles with samples were kept in muffle furnace and left it at 550°C for 4 hrs. for ashing. After completing the 4 hrs. The ash content was calculated by knowing the difference between the initial and final weight of samples.

$$\text{Ash content} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W}$$

Where,

W_1 = Weight of the empty crucible, (g)

W_2 = Final weight of the crucible with the ash, (g)

W = Weight of the sample, (g)

2.3.6 Fiber content: Fiber content in Mahua seeds was estimated by using Fibra Plus Extraction unit (FRB-6). Fiber estimation process was completed mainly in two steps namely acid and alkali wash. 2 gm of defatted sample was taken in a crucible. Crucibles were placed on heating plate and allowed for boiling and refluxed simultaneously for 45-minute at 500°C in acid wash (1.25%) and later after beaker and residue were washed with distilled water until the filtrate was neutral. In base wash, again residue was washing with NaOH (1.25%). Afterwards, crucible with sample is dried in oven at 100°C for 1-2 hours. Then the samples were transferred in ashing crucible and kept in muffle furnace at 550°C for 4 hr. The fiber content was calculated by using following formula.

$$\text{Fibre Content} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W}$$

Where,

W = Weight of sample, (g)

W_1 = Crucible weight before ashing, (g)

W_2 = Crucible weight after ashing, (g)

2.3.7 Total Carbohydrate content: carbohydrate content was determined by using Anthrone reagent method described in Sadashivam and Manickam., (2023). The amount of total carbohydrate was expressed as following formula

$$\text{Amount of carbohydrate (100mg of sample)} = \frac{\text{mg of glucose}}{\text{volume of test sample}} \times 100$$

2.4 Chemical properties of Mahua Oil:

2.4.1 Acid Value: The acid value is defined as the number of milligrams of Potassium hydroxide required to neutralize the free fatty acids present in one gram of fat. Acid value of oil sample was determined by using manual of FSSAI 02.009:2021. 2.5 g of oil sample was measured accurately using scientific weighing balance (Shimadzu, ATX224). Then 50 ml ethyl alcohol was added with about 1 ml of phenolphthalein indicator solution. Swirl to dissolve the sample. After then sample mixture was Heated in water bath (Bio Technics, India) for about 15 to 20 min at 80°C. Titration was conducted while hot against standard alkali solution shaking vigorously during titrating. At the End point using phenolphthalein indicator shall be from colourless to light pink. Persisting for around 15 seconds. Acid value calculated by following formula

$$\text{Acid value} = \frac{40 \times V \times N}{W}$$

Where:

V- Volume in ml of standard sodium hydroxide used

N- Normality of sodium hydroxide solution

W- Weight in g of the sample

2.4.2 Free Fatty Acid: Free fatty acid is measure of acid present in oil sample. Free fatty acid can be determined by using the same procedure discussed in Acid value determination method (FSSAI 02.009:2021). The acidity is frequently expressed as the percentage of FFA in the sample also.

$$\text{Acid value} = \% \text{ fatty acid (as oleic)} \times 1.99$$

2.4.3 Peroxide Value: Peroxide is measure of substances are generally products of fat oxidation. It represents in terms of milliequivalents of peroxide per 1000 grams of sample determined by using the method described in AOCS, Cd 8b-90.5 g oil sample was taken in 250 mL conical flask. Then 30 mL of the 3:2 acetic acid-chloroform solution was added. Swirl to dissolve the sample in solution. After then 0.5 mL of saturated potassium iodide (KI) solution was added. Allow the solution to stand with occasional shaking, and then 30 mL of distilled water added immediately. Titrate with 0.1 N sodium thiosulfate. Continue the titration until the yellow iodine colour has almost disappeared. about 2.0 mL of starch indicator

solution was added. Continue the titration with constant agitation. Add the thiosulfate solution dropwise until the blue colour just disappears. Peroxide value (milliequivalents peroxide/1000 g sample) calculated by following:

$$\text{Peroxide value} = \frac{(S - B) \times N \times 1000}{\text{Mass of sample(g)}}$$

where:

S- Volume of the titrant, ml of sample

B- Volume of the titrant, ml of blank

N- Normality of sodium thiosulfate solution.

2.4.4 Saponification value: saponification value is amount of base required to saponify per gram of oil sample. Saponification value is determined by method described in manual of FSSAI 02.007:2021. 2 gm of oil sample was mixed with 25 ml of alcoholic potassium hydroxide, then refluxed in water bath (Bio Technics, India) until saponification is complete. Wash the condenser with ethanol. Solution was Titrated with 0.5 N hydrochloric acid using phenolphthalein as indicator. Saponification value was calculated by following formula:

$$\text{Saponification value} = \frac{56.1 \times (B - S) \times N}{W}$$

Where,

B = Volume in mL of standard hydrochloric acid required for the blank.

S = Volume in mL of standard hydrochloric acid required for the sample

N = Normality of the standard hydrochloric acid and

W = Weight in g of the oil/fat taken for the test

2.4.5 Radical scavenging activity (DPPH): The Radical scavenging activity of oil was determined using DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging method as described by Cisneros *et al.* (2014). Extract solution was prepared by using slightly modified method performed by Cisneros *et al.* (2014). 1 g oil sample vigorously mixed with 1 ml of n-hexane then 1 ml of methanol (80%, v/v) was added. shake the solution in rotary shaker (Remi, RS-24BL) in 150 rpm for 1 hour. After centrifugation at 6000 rpm for 15 min methanolic solution portion was used as an extract for determination of antioxidant properties. Extract solution were stored in dark-coloured bottles to protect it from direct sunlight and heat. The absorbance of the control (DPPH solution) and oil reaction mixtures was measured at 515 nm with UV-spectrophotometer (model, 3375). The RSA was calculated using the following equation. (Muangrat *et al.*, 2018)

$$\text{Radical Scavenging Activity (\%)} = \left[\frac{A_c - A_{30}}{A_c} \right]$$

Where,

A_c- The absorbance of control DPPH solution

A₃₀- the absorbance o sample after 30 min of incubation

2.4.6 Total phenolic content (TPC): The total phenolic content was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. The total phenol concentration in the sample was calculated from the graph and expressed as mg of gallic acid equivalent per 1000 grams (mg GAE/1000g) (Muangrat *et al.*, 2018). The total phenolic compound content was analysed using the Folin-Ciocalteu spectrophotometric method modified by Cisneros *et al.* (2014). Same Extract was used in TPC determination. A volume of 250 µL of the methanolic extract of the oil sample was diluted with 1750 µL of the methanol solution (80%) to make the volume up to 2 ml in each test tube, after then 1 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was added and mixed for 3 min. After 3 min, 1 ml of sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃, 10%) was added after agitation. After the incubation period of 90 min in the dark, the absorbance at wave length 725 nm measured against blank. The determination of total phenolic content was compared to a standard curve of gallic acid solutions and expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalents per gram of the oil sample (mg GAE/g oil sample).

3. Result and discussion

3.1 Physical properties of mahua seeds: The physical properties seed sample including dimensions, bulk density, true density, porosity, angle of repose, and coefficient of static friction were determined and were presented in Table. 1 with their standard deviation. The length, width and thickness of seeds were found to be 22.76 mm, 11.42 mm, and 6.38 mm respectively. Sahu *et al.*, (2022) reported similar range of dimensions. The value of bulk density of mahua seed was found to be 498.36±7.55 kg/m³. The true density of seed was 1009±10.81 kg/m³. The porosity of mahua seed was found to be 50.2±2.2%. The angle of repose of mahua seed was found to be 37.19° which was in range determined by Sahu *et al.*, (2022) in their study i.e., 41°. The coefficient of friction of the samples was determined within the moisture content of 4.8-5.2% (wb). The coefficient of friction was measured on four surfaces, namely glass, stainless steel, galvanised steel, and mild steel sheet. The value of coefficient of friction for mahua seeds for different surfaces i.e., glass, stainless steel, galvanised steel, and mild steel were 0.3057, 0.2125, 0.3057 and 0.2867 respectively. Sahu *et al.*, (2022) reported similar results for mahua seed.

Table 1 Physical properties of Mahua seed

S.no	Parameters	Mean ± SD	
1.	Dimensions (mm)	Length	22.76 ± 3.32
		Width	11.42 ± 1.62
		Thickness	6.38 ± 1.24
2.	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	498.36 ± 7.55	
3.	True density (kg/m ³)	1009 ± 10.81	
4.	Porosity (%)	50.2 ± 2.02	
5.	Angle of repose	37.19° ± 2.60	
6.	Coefficient of friction	Glass	0.3057 ± 0.012
		Stainless Steel	0.2125 ± 0.0105
		Galvanised steel	0.3057 ± 0.1566
		Mild steel	0.2867 ± 0.0108

Chemical composition of Mahua seeds:

The proximate composition of mahua seeds were calculated by standard method and the results were shown in the Table.2. The proximate analysis indicated that the mahua seeds were the rich source of oil i.e., 41% (w/w) and the carbohydrate content was 24%. The other proximate composition of mahua seeds were recorded as moisture content 4.8% (wb), ash content 3.9%, protein content 15.34%, fiber content 3.57%. All the proximate compositions were

shown in Table.2 with mean values of observations with their standard deviation values. Mishra and Pradhan, (2013) reported that mahua seed contains 33 to 43% oil by weight or kernel. According to Singhal *et al.*, 1986 mahua seed oil per cent varies from 40-51% in weight basis. Proximate composition was in range with the results by Mohammad *et al.*, 2016 reported. In antioxidant analysis of mahua seeds RSA (DPPH) and TPC (mg GAE/kg oil) recorded 79.38±1.52 % and 1.59±0.18 mg GAE/kg oil respectively.

Table 2 composition of mahua seed

S.no	Properties	Mean± SD
1.	Moisture content (% , wb)	4.80 ± 0.39
2.	Oil content (%)	41 ± 1.102
3.	Ash content (%)	3.19 ± 0.18
4.	Crude protein (%)	15.34 ± 0.39
5.	Fibre content (%)	3.57 ± 0.707
6.	Carbohydrate (%)	24 ± 0.81
7.	Radical scavenging activity% (DPPH)	79.3874±1.5219
8.	Total Phenolic Content (mg GAE/kg oil)	1.5922±0.1866

Physio-chemical properties of oil: chemical composition of extracted mahuseeds oil were calculated by standard method and the results were shown in the Table.3. The physical properties of specific gravity and refractive index of oil were recorded 0.908±0.003 and 1.4638±0.0003 respectively. Like the values obtained by Singh Singh.,1991. the acid value of mahua oil was found 10.4 ±1.08 mgKOH/g of oil with 5.20±0.56 free fatty acid content, AV and FFA value of oil was more in compared with the study of Munasinghe *et*

al., 2016. Peroxides presents in oil was 9.8±0.77 meq/kg oil. Mahua seed oil high in saponification value recorded as 185.39±6.27 mg KOH/ g oil, Kumar *et al.*, 2018 also recorded similar PV and SV in their studies of mahua oil. Antioxidants quality of mahua seed oil, which includes radical scavenging activity (DPPH) and total phenolic content values, which was 42.08 ±1.10% and 14.38 ±1.60 mg GAE/kg oil respectively. Similar values were reviewed by Sinha *et al.*, 2017.

Table 3 Properties of mahua seed oil

OIL PROPERTIES	VALUES
1. Specific gravity	0.908±0.003
2. Refractive index (at 25°C in nD)	1.4638±0.0003
3. Acid value (mgKOH/g)	10.4±1.08
4. Free Fatty Acid (%)	5.20±0.56
5. Saponification value (mg KOH/g oil)	185.39±6.27
6. Peroxide value (meq./kg oil)	9.8±0.77
7. Radical scavenging activity% (DPPH)	42.08±1.10
8. Total Phenolic Content (mg GAE/kg oil)	14.38±1.60

Conclusion:

From the preceding research, the physicochemical properties of mahua seed and oil, including physical properties true density, bulk density, angle of repose, coefficient of friction, proximate composition of oil, protein, ash, fibre, carbohydrate, and AV, FFA, PV, SV, RSA (DPPH) and TPC were examined. Oil content of mahua seed was higher than other proximate constitute. The peroxide value and acid value were higher but below the maximum limits specified for human consumption.

References:

1. **A.O.A.C. 2000.** Official methods of analysis, Association of Official Analytical Chemistry, 16th Ed. Washington DC., U.S.A.
2. **A.O.C.S. Official (2003).** Sampling and analysis of commercial fats and oils.
3. **Anamika Thakur¹, MZ Siddiqui², Ranjit Singh¹, Niranjana Prasad³ 2018,** Comparative Study Of Physiochemical Properties Of Chironji (*Buchanania Lanza*) Gum And Bahera (*Terminalia bellerica*) gum, Vol. Viii, Issue Special(C) , August 2018 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, pp 138-139.
4. **Atabani A.E., Silitonga A.S., Mahlia T.M.I.M.I., Masjuki H.H.H., Badrudding I.A., Fayaz H. (2013).** Non-edible oils: a critical evaluation of oil extraction, fatty acid composition, biodiesel production, characteristic, engine performance and emission production. *Renew Sustain Energy.* 18:211–245.
5. **Cisneros, Daniel P., Adrian A., and Luis C.Z. Chemical Composition. (2014).** Oxidative Stability and Antioxidant Capacity of Oil Extracted from Roasted Seeds of Sacha-Inchi (*Plukenetia volubilis* L.). *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 62, 5191–5197.
6. **Ekkaa E., and Ekka N.S. (2014).** Madhuca longifolia var. latifolia: An Important Medicinal Plant used by tribes of North-East part of Chhattisgarh. *International*

Interdisciplinary Research Journal, ISSN 2249-9598, Vol-IV.

7. **FSSAI. (2021).** Manual of methods of analysis of foods: Oils and Fats.
8. **Marikkar J.M.N., Ghazali H.M., and Long K. (2010).** Composition and Thermal Characteristics of Madhuca longifolia Seed Fat and Its Solid and Liquid Fractions. *Japan Oil Chemists' Society J. Oleo Sci.* 59, (1) 7-14.
9. **Mishra S., and Pradhan S. (2013).** Mahua (Madhuca Indica) A Review of Its Traditional Uses and Nutritional Properties. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 2(5):30-36.
10. **Mohamed F. Ramadan et al. (2016).** Functional characteristics, nutritional value and industrial applications of Madhuca longifolia seeds: an overview. *J Food Sci Technol*, 53(5):2149–2157.
11. **Muangrat R., Pattawee V., Narirat C. (2018),** Screw press extraction of Sacha inchi seeds: Oil yield and its chemical composition and antioxidant properties. *J Food Process Preserv.* 2018;e13635.
12. **Munasinghe M., and Wansapala J. (2016).** Oil extraction from Madhuca longifolia (J. Konig) J.F. Macbr seeds and evaluation of physico-chemical properties, fatty acid profile, antioxidant potential and sensory characteristic. *Trop. Agric. (Trinidad) Vol.-93 No. 1.*
13. **Sadasivam S., and Manickam A., 2023.** Biochemical methods (fourth edition). New age international (P) Ltd., New Delhi.
14. **Sahu F.M., Suthar S.H., Sharma V.K., and Shrivastava A. (2022).** Moisture dependent physical properties of Mahua seed (Madhuca longifolia) *The Pharma Innovation Journal* 2022; 11(11): 624-630.
15. **Singhal K.K., Cbahil S.M., and Sharma D.D. (1986).** Versatile mahua (madhuca indica) seed cake a review. *Agric. Res.* 7-(2) : 105-123.

16. **Singh A. and Singh I.S. (1991)**. Chemical Evaluation of Mahua (*Madhuca indica*) Seed. *Food Chem&try* 40, 221-228
17. **Suri K., Singh B., Kaur A., and Singh N. (2019)**. Impact of roasting and extraction methods on chemical properties, oxidative stability and Maillard reaction products of peanut oils. *J Food Sci Technol*.
18. **Thilakarathna R.C.N., Fong Siow L., Tang T.K, Chan E.S. and Lee (2023)**. Physicochemical and antioxidative properties of ultrasound-assisted extraction of mahua (*Madhuca longifolia*) seed oil in comparison with conventional Soxhlet and mechanical extractions. *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry* 92, 06280.
19. **Kumar D., Chibber V.K., and Singh A. (2018)**. Physical and Chemical Properties of Mahua and Sal Seed Oils. Springer Nature Singapore Pte Ltd.
20. **Sinha J., Singh V., Singh J. and Rai A.K. (2017)**. Phytochemistry, Ethnomedical Uses and Future Prospects of Mahua (*Madhuca longifolia*) as a Food: A Review. *Nutr Food Sci*, 7:1 DOI: 10.4172/2155-9600.1000573